

Application of vertical switching signal prediction based on ship networking in heterogeneous networks

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Abstract: With the rise of ship networking, in view of the coexistence of many heterogeneous networks, the vertical switching technology of heterogeneous networks is studied, and a vertical signal prediction algorithm is proposed by using grey theory. Through the simulation analysis of MATLAB test, it is verified that the algorithm can effectively improve the accuracy of the prediction signal and is suitable for ship terminals.

Keywords: Ship Networking, Heterogeneous Network, Vertical Switching, Prediction Algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

The inland river resources of our country are very rich, the ship transportation industry has the profound history, the colleague occupies the very large proportion in the national economy. Computer technology and Internet technology are becoming more and more mature, so the Internet of things is developing rapidly, which promotes the replacement and upgrading of modern information industry after Internet and mobile interconnection. Therefore, the shipping industry has put forward higher requirements for water traffic technology. By referring to the concept and technology of Internet of things, the architecture of ship networking is constructed to promote the rapid development and wide application of ship networking technology. The "shipping network" is in fact the hope that the concepts, methods and methods related to the Internet of things will be able to be linked to the Internet of things. The results are applied to ship transportation, in short, to connect ships through the network. Therefore, the foundation of ship networking is realized when establishing a comprehensive real-time wireless network connection. The complex geographical location of the ocean, the relatively bad climate conditions and the low average density of user distribution all lead to the relatively difficult realization

of wireless network technology. According to the present situation and service requirements of different networks, how to select the appropriate available networks adaptively at different times, and how to realize the vertical switching between heterogeneous networks in time and effectively, need to be solved urgently according to the different areas covered by different networks. The key is how to keep network services from different heterogeneous networks Select the network signal of good quality. In addition, it is also very important to predict the network signal. By predicting the parameters of the network signal, the ship terminal can judge whether it is necessary to switch the network, and be prepared when switching is needed, which greatly improves the switching rate and saves resources.

II. NETWORK SWITCHING AND HETEROGENEOUS NETWORK RELATED TECHNOLOGY

Mobile handover refers to the process of converting a mobile user in the call establishment state or call state to a new traffic channel in the process of mobile communication under the premise of ensuring uninterrupted communication. The handover process can be divided into three stages: network measurement,

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handover decision and handover execution, as shown in Fig.1 .The process of network measurement is to detect and discover whether there is a network available in the current area and to obtain the relevant network parameters of the switchable network, so as to prepare for the handover judgment in advance. Switching judgment needs a judgment mechanism, which involves a variety of algorithms, and it is also the main attack point of each researcher. What conditions can be met to carry out the network? Switch. The network parameters obtained in the previous step of network detection are the data sources and basis for switching judgment. After judging that switching can be made, switching can be performed, and handover is also an important aspect. Because of the differences between heterogeneous networks, how to achieve efficient communication between networks with different structures is also a problem worthy of further study. Therefore, various switching methods and switching algorithms are mainly to solve two problems, namely, the allocation of limited resources and the switching decision problem.

Fig.1 Switch the three stages of the decision

There are many types of network switching. According to different standards, there can be a variety of classification methods, the common classification methods are shown in figure 2 [1]

Fig.2 Network switching classification

The handover of the wireless network in mobile

communication is divided into horizontal switching and vertical switching. Horizontal switching refers to switching between the same network types, such as switching between different cells in GSM networks, and vertical switching is worth switching between different types of networks, such as switching between WLAN access points and cellular network base stations.

III. VERTICAL SWITCHING ALGORITHM BASED ON GREY THEORY

The grey system theory takes the "small sample" and "poor information" uncertainty system as the research object, and the restriction on the data and its distribution is small. Through the generation, development and extraction of valuable information to realize the accurate description and understanding of the real world, it has strong practicability and maneuverability. In this paper, the grey prediction theory will be used to design the vertical switching algorithm, which aims to predict the time when the characteristic quantity reaches a certain characteristic quantity at a certain time in the future by using a series of response prediction object related characteristics measured at an equal time interval.

Wireless signal RSS characteristics

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A. Wireless signal RSS characteristics

The wireless signals received by the ship during navigation are dynamically changing. The wireless signal of mobile communication has the problem of fast fading and slow fading and path loss.

Fast fading is mainly caused by multipath propagation. In reality, there are many objects between the transmitting tower and the terminal, which have physical properties of scattering, reflection and refraction of electromagnetic waves, thus causing

multipath transmission of wireless signals. The signals transmitted from the base station are superimposed with the arrival signals after passing through various propagation paths. The resultant signals show rapid fluctuation, and the change rate is much faster than the slow fading, so it is also called short-term fading.

Slow fading is mainly. The received signal strength is decreased [2]. Due to a shadow effect caused by an obstacle, but because the signal strength value is mainly changed with the change of the geographical position, the change is relatively slow, and is referred to as slow fading. The slow fading obeys the log positive distribution and is related to the position of the terminal, and the speed of the fading is related to the speed of the terminal movement. The received signal presents an irregular variation over time which has a very serious effect on the quality of the transmission signal and the reliability of the transmission signal, which may cause an interruption of the propagation of information when the slow fading is severe. The slow fading is mainly caused by the change of the structure of the transmission medium, slow fading is caused by the change of mean atmospheric conditions such as atmospheric turbulence, atmospheric refraction and atmospheric junction, which is usually not related to frequency, but mainly related to meteorological conditions, topography and other factors. The path loss varies with the distance between the transmitting base station and the receiving terminal. The radio waves are subjected to the diffusion effect in the transmission process and the loss in the transmission space. The closer to the transmitting base station, the higher the RSS, the farther away from the base station, the lower the RSS [3].

$$P[d(t)] = [d(t)]^{-n} \square S[d(t)] \square K[d(t)]$$

In the form: $[d(t)]^{-n}$ for a large range of path losses;
 $S[d(t)]$ for medium range slow fading $K[d(t)]$

for a small range of fast fading. Fast fading is that it changes rapidly with time and knows the extent of decline. Slow fading is slow with time, and the range of change is also large. The law of path loss is that the closer the terminal is to the transmitter, the stronger the receiving power of the terminal is. When the RSS value of the wireless signal is collected, the filter processing is carried out first to eliminate the influence of the fast fading on the RSS value as far as possible, leaving the

slow fading and the path loss. Make the RSS value relatively smooth and improve the accuracy of the prediction.

B. Median processing

For the collected RSS signal, it has to be filtered in real time, and the algorithm is simple, so it is suitable for shipborne terminal. In this paper, the median processing

Method is adopted. Let the original RSS signal sequence be listed as

$$P_1 P_2 P_3 P_4 P_5 \dots P_n \tag{1}$$

The filtered sequence is as follows:

$$Q_1 Q_2 Q_3 Q_4 Q_5 \dots Q_n \tag{2}$$

$$\text{When } n=1, P_n = Q_n \tag{3}$$

$$\text{When } n>1 \text{ 时, } Q_{n2} = (Q_{n1} - Q_{n-1}) / 2 + Q_{n-1} \tag{4}$$

$$Q_n = (P_n - Q_{n-1}) / 2 + Q_{n-1} \tag{5}$$

The cubic mean processing method can not only filter the wave in real time, but also achieve the ideal effect.

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{n1} &= (P_n - Q_{n-1}) / 2 + Q_{n-1} \\ Q_n &= (Q_{n2} - Q_{n-1}) / 2 + Q_{n-1} \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

C. GM (1, 1) prediction model

GM (1, 1) model is the most widely used grey dynamic prediction model in grey system theory, which belongs to the first order grey prediction model with single variable. When using GM (1, 1) model to predict the data, it has the characteristics of less original data demand, less computation and high accuracy. Therefore, this method has a wide range of practical value. In this paper, the GM (1, 1) prediction model is used to obtain the median value of fading signals. It is used in switching algorithm [5]. Assume that the received signal strength sequence of the sampling point is:

$$X^{(0)} = \{x^{(0)}(1), x^{(0)}(2), \dots, x^{(0)}(n)\} \quad (7)$$

Do an accumulation to generate a new data sequence column

$$X^{(1)} = \{x^{(1)}(1), x^{(1)}(2), \dots, x^{(1)}(n)\} \quad (8)$$

Of which:

$$x^{(0)}(i) = \sum_{j=1}^i x^{(0)}(j) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (9)$$

P represents the gray level of development and Q indicates the action of ash..

$$\frac{dx^{(1)}}{dt} + px^{(1)} = q \quad (10)$$

The grey prediction equation is obtained.

$$x^{(1)}(i+1) = \left[x^{(0)}(1) - \frac{q}{p} \right] e^{-pi} + \frac{q}{p} (i=1, 2, \dots, n) \quad (11)$$

The cumulative matrices A and Y are constructed.

$$Y = (x^{(0)}(2), x^{(0)}(3), \dots, x^{(0)}(n))^T \quad (12)$$

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} -0.5(x^{(1)}(1) + x^{(1)}(2)) & 1 \\ -0.5(x^{(1)}(2) + x^{(1)}(3)) & 1 \\ \dots & \dots \\ -0.5(x^{(1)}(n-1) + x^{(1)}(n)) & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Using the least square to estimate the parameter vector:

$$\alpha = (p, q)^T = (A^T A)^{-1} A^T Y_n \quad (14)$$

The derivation and reduction are carried out, and the following results are obtained:

$$x^{(0)}(i+1) = (1 - e^p) \left[x^{(0)}(1) - \frac{q}{p} \right] e^{-pi} \quad (15)$$

Set up $x^{(1)}(0) = x^{(0)}(1)$ The prediction equation is obtained as follows:

$$x^{(1)}(i+1) = \left[x^{(0)}(1) - \frac{q}{p} \right] e^{-pi} + \frac{q}{p} (i=0, 1, \dots, n) \quad (16)$$

$$x^{(0)}(i+1) = x^{(1)}(i+1) - x^{(1)}(i)$$

If the signal receiving intensity of the ship terminal at t time is at t time, the n-dimension sequence is formed together with the previous N-1 sampling value, that is to say, the n-dimension sequence is composed of the signal receiving intensity of the ship terminal at t time.

$$X_n^{(0)} = \{x^{(0)}(t-n+1), x^{(0)}(t-n+2), \dots, x^{(0)}(t)\} \quad (17)$$

Therefore, the grey prediction formula of w-step received signal RSS can be obtained as follows:

$$x^{(0)}(t+w) = \left[x^{(0)}(t-n+1) - \frac{q}{p} \right] (1 - e^p) e^{-p(t+w-1)} \quad (18)$$

Due to the shadow effect caused by obstacles, the received signal is distorted, which will increase the error rate of switching. Therefore, before using grey prediction theory, the received signal must be smoothed and preprocessed. The weight East China average method is used to process the time series d (n).

$$\bar{d}(n) = \begin{cases} d(0), n = 0 \\ (1 - \alpha)\bar{d}(n-1) + \alpha d(n), n > 0 \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

IV. ALGORITHM IMPLEMENTATION

If the wireless resources of the target access network are rich enough and superior to the current network, the prediction algorithm of the vertical switching trigger time is implemented as shown in the figure. the shipboard terminal selects one or several targets to access the network based on the network signal intensity change trend of the detected area coverage. the type of vertical switching is analyzed to estimate the switching time and the prediction step size. At the same time, the target access network is preprocessed with time series, and then the received signal is calculated

with p-step gray prediction. When the target access network meets the decision condition of switching, it can stop the prediction and execute the switching. The implementation of vertical switching algorithm is shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3 Flow chart of prediction algorithm

Fig.4 Comparison between RSS prediction value and actual received value

A. Authors and Affiliations

When the simulation is verified, let the ship speed be 15 m/s and the sampling interval be 0.1 s. the data of the first 30 points are used as the observation sequence to predict the data of the last 30 points, and the interval between the sampling points is 2 m, that is, the RSS

before 60 m can be predicted. After the experiment, if the prediction distance is too short, the simulation effect is not good, the fusion cannot play a lifting role, and the signal prediction time is too short to play the role of switching early warning. But the prediction distance is too long, the accuracy of the prediction value and the fusion value is greatly reduced, and the prediction significance is lost. The results show that the data of 60 m can be taken into account. Forecast time and accuracy.

The simulation results show that when the weight of the predicted value is 0.7 and the average weight of the information center is 0.3, the error between the predicted value and the true value is the highest, up to 35%, as shown in the table.

Tab.1. The Coefficient selection of needed point of 30, prediction point of 60

	Weight of predicted value							
	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9
Information center average weight	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.1
Absolute value difference of error lift/%	-72	-40	-16	8	27	37	29	15

As listed in the Table2, the error between the average value of the information center and the real value is mainly due to the fact that the real value is affected by fast fading and slow fading on the basis of the path loss. The filtered value is an RSS change value that is relatively smooth after the fast fading is filtered out, so the error is minimized. The prediction error is mainly due to the condition that the front 60m is to be predicted, and the crossing amplitude is relatively large, so that the accuracy is reduced. And the value of the average value of the fusion information center and the value of the predicted value are greatly improved with respect to the accuracy of the fused value. The degree of improvement of the predicted value is up to 35% with respect to the more accurate prediction value. So use the fusion value as the front RSS It can provide a relatively accurate basis for switching pre-decision.

Tab.2 The Comparison of absolute value of deviation when choosing the weights of 0.7and 0.3

category	Average information center	Predictive value	The fusion value
Absolute difference	3.04	1.76	1.20

The average value of fading channel and information center is simulated by Matlab, and the predicted value of RSS is compared. Due to the influence of slow fading, the RSS received once sailing deviates greatly from the average value of information center. The predicted value is close to the filter value, but there is also an error. However, the fusion value of the average value of the information center and the predicted value is very close to the real value, as shown in the table, the average value of a single error is only 1.24 dB. When the ship is sailing, the ship will soon enter the coverage of a base station, but the signal from this base station has not yet been received. At this time, it can be received by the information center. Forward network status values. At this time the ship terminal takes the average value sent by the information center as the forecast value of the forward network value as the switching warning reference.

IV. CONCLUSION

In view of the coexistence of many heterogeneous networks in inland waterway shipping, this paper analyzes the difficulties and key techniques in vertical switching of heterogeneous networks. A vertical switching signal prediction technique based on grey theory and RSS value is proposed, and the correctness and reliability of the algorithm are proved by experimental simulation. Although the algorithm can basically achieve signal prediction, but there are still some errors, but the existence of these errors is allowed, and the switching judgment algorithm can make up for the shortcomings of the prediction algorithm. Switching judgment algorithm can make up for the shortcomings of the prediction algorithm.

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